

The Influence of Quality of Complaints Handling Services and Customer Choices on Hotel Customer Loyalty

^{1*}Dian Primanita Oktasari, ¹Tine Yuliantini,²Rahayu Lestari, and ²Nunu Nurjaya

¹Departement of Management, Universitas Mercu Buana, Indonesia

²Departement of Management, Universitas Nasional, Indonesia

Abstract: This study aims to analyze the effect of service quality, complaint handling and customer trust on customer loyalty. In this study using primary data obtained from distributing questionnaires to 100 MeruyaFave Hotel customers. This research uses descriptive analysis and inferential analysis, and analyzed using multiple linear regression correlation analysis, the model feasibility test, and hypothesis testing. The results of this study indicate that there is a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

The results of the multiple linear regression equation are $Y = 1.190 + 0.319 X_1 + 0.343 X_2 + 0.295 X_3$. The feasibility test of the model in the R² test shows that service quality, complaint handling and customer trust have an effect of 82.2% on customer loyalty. On the results of hypothesis testing (t test) there was a significant value on the quality of service variable of 0.005, a significant value on the complaint handling variable of 0,000, and a significant value of customer trust variables of 0.006, it can be concluded that partially the three independent variables had a positive influence and Significant to the dependent variable is the customer loyalty variable Fave Hotel Meruya.

Keywords: Service Quality, Complaints Handling, Customer Trust, Customer Loyalty

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of the business world today is growing rapidly, so that competition between companies is very tight. Every company leader wants his company to be the best among other companies. Each company creates an effective strategy to make the company the best and can survive in the existing competition. To face competition, an appropriate marketing strategy is needed to face the challenges of competition.

Gaining competitive advantage is a major challenge for companies operating in today's business environment, both the manufacturing sector and the service sector. The service sector is currently growing more rapidly, especially in the hotel sector. Hotel is a type of accommodation that uses a part or the whole building to provide accommodation services, food and beverages and other supporting services to the public that are managed commercially. One of the hotels in Jakarta is Fave Hotel Meruya, West Jakarta. Fave Hotel Meruya West Jakarta is a three-star hotel that was built in a strategic location in West Jakarta.

Customer loyalty has an important role in the company (Ristanti, et al, 2011). Customer loyalty in general, can be interpreted as someone's loyalty to a product, both certain goods, and services. Customer loyalty can be reflected in the customer's habits in purchasing services continuously and repeatedly. According to Kotler and Keller (2012), Loyalty is a commitment that is held firm to repurchase or subscribe to a choice of products or services in the future even though situational influences and marketing efforts have the potential to cause consumers to switch to other products.

Another factor that influences customer loyalty is handling complaints. Complaints handling is considered very important because in the flower of service complaint handling is one type of exception. Customer complaints are emotional expressions of customers because of something that is unacceptable, both related to the product offered and to the service (Sangadji and Sopiah, 2013). Handling complaints is an important part of the strategy to keep customers loyal to the company (Feriyanto and Triana, 2015). This is consistent with Juan Soleman Supit's (2015) study which states that customer loyalty is influenced by complaint handling.

Customer trust is the foundation of the business of a business transaction between two or more parties will occur if trust each other. This customer's trust cannot be easily recognized by other parties or business partners, but must be built from scratch and can be proven. If there is no trust, it's likely that the customer will not become loyal. Customer trust has been considered as an influence in various transactions between sellers and buyers so that customer satisfaction can be realized as expected. This is consistent with Ellena's (2011) research which states that customer loyalty is influenced by customer trust. Customer trust is one of the factors that influence customer loyalty. According to Jasfar (2009) trust is the glue that enables companies to trust others in organizing and using resources effectively in creating added value.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

Service Quality

Service has different characteristics from other aspects. According to Tjiptono (2012) stated that services have four main characteristics, namely: a) Intangibility (Intangibility) services are not real, not the same as physical products (goods). Services cannot be seen, felt, smelled, or heard before being purchased. To reduce uncertainty, service buyers will look for signs or evidence of service quality, ie from the place, people, equipment, communication tools, symbols, and prices they see. Therefore, the duty of the service provider is to manage the evidence that manifests the intangible. b) Inseparability in general, services produced (produced) and felt at the same time, henceforth if desired by one person to be submitted to another party, then he will still be part of the service. c) Variability of services varies greatly because it depends on who, when and where the service is provided. d) Perishability of services cannot be saved. The durability of a service will not be a problem if demand is always present and certain, because producing services in advance is easy. When requests change up and down, difficult problems will arise immediately.

Complaints Handling

Complaints are not something that is always seen as negative, but are also seen as something positive because of the source of learning, a valuable input for companies to improve their service performance. The first thing to do to deal with customer complaints is to quickly stop the customer's anger. After everything is revealed, the customer is satisfied that he has issued a steam and becomes rational again, then we try to solve the problem and provide a solution. Complaints according to Wahjono (2010) basically relate to three main sources, namely 40% of problems caused by companies, such as low product quality, inaccurate and excessive communication or information, prices that are too expensive, etc. 20% of problems are caused by employees, for example rude and disrespectful attitudes and behavior. 40% comes from the customer himself, for example not careful reading instructions or instructions given excessive expectations, etc.

Consumer Choice

Consumer decision / choice is an action taken by consumers to buy a product / service. Each producer must run a variety of strategies so that consumers decide to buy products or services.

According to Kotler (2012), purchasing decisions are actions of consumers to want to buy or not to product. Of the various factors that influence consumers in purchasing a product or service, consumers usually always consider the quality, price and products that are already known by the public.

Before consumers decide to buy, consumers usually go through several stages in advance, namely, (1) problem recognition, (2) information retrieval. (3) Alternative evaluation, (4) buying decision or not, (5) post-purchase behavior. Another understanding of purchasing decisions according to Schiffman and Kanuk (2000) is "the selection of an option from two or alternative choices". Can be interpreted, the purchase decision is a decision of someone where he chose one of several alternative choices available.

Customer Loyalty

Loyalty is without coercion, and from self-awareness. Efforts are made to create customer satisfaction to influence consumer attitudes in determining goods / services. Because, current purchasing decisions can affect future buying decisions (Rekart, 2008). According to Kotler and Keller (2012) loyalty is a firm commitment to repurchase or subscribe to a choice of product or service in the future even though situational influences and marketers' efforts have the potential to cause consumers to switch to other products.

According to Lovelock and Jochen (2011), customer loyalty is the customer's willingness to continue to subscribe to a company in the long run, by buying and using goods and services repeatedly and even better exclusively, and voluntarily recommending them to other parties. Because, current purchasing decisions can influence future buying decisions (Rekarti, 2008). Customer loyalty is a behavioral impulse to make repeated purchases and to build customer loyalty to a product or service produced by the business entity takes a long time through a process of repeated purchases. Loyalty can be formed from good service quality.

According to Sugiyono (2013), the hypothesis is a temporary answer to the research problem formulation. The purpose of doing a hypothesis is to find out how much will be done in solving certain problems. Based on the analysis framework above:

Figure 1. Research Conceptual Framework

H1: Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Fave Hotel Meruya's Customer Loyalty in West Jakarta

H2: Complaints Handling has a positive and significant effect on Fave Hotel Meruya Customer Loyalty in West Jakarta

H3: Customer Choice has a positive and significant effect on Fave Hotel Meruya's Customer Loyalty in West Jakarta

III .RESEARCH METHODE

In this study using two methods of data analysis namely descriptive analysis and inferential analysis

Descriptive Analysis Method

According to Sugiyono (2012: 206) Descriptive method is a method used to analyze data by describing or describing data that has been collected as it is without intending to make conclusions that apply to the public or generalization. In this case the writer will analyze the data that will relate to the quality of service, handling complaints and customer trust.

Inferential Analysis Method

In this method, the authors test and estimate the variables that are the focus of the research, namely, service quality, complaint handling, customer satisfaction, customer trust (as the independent variable) and customer loyalty (as the dependent variable).

In this study the authors used multiple analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis is a method of analysis used to determine the accuracy of predictions of the influence that occurs between the independent variable (X) against the dependent variable (Y). The formula for multiple linear regression is as follows:

$$y = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + e$$

y = Customer Loyalty

a = Constant

x₁ = Service Quality

x₂ = Complaints Handling

x₃ = Customer trust

e = Standard Estimation Error

IV.RESULT

The hypothesis test that is conducted concludes the result as follows.

H1 is accepted: The influence of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty

The results of the mean quality of service (X1) as a whole identify that the quality of service gets a good value. From the biggest mean, the fourth and fifth questions obtained were 4.46, namely the employees of Fave Hotel Kembangan giving attention in service without differentiating customers and Fave Hotel Kembangan has attractive facilities and interiors.

According to Tjiptono (2012) defining service quality is a measure of how well the level of service provided is able to match customer expectations. If the services provided provide the appropriate expectations, the customer will be loyal to the company / product. Good service quality will give a good impact for the company because it will be a loyal customer and provide benefits for the company.

This is supported based on the results of previous studies by Safitri (2016) which states that service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

A conclusion section must be included and should indicate clearly the advantages, limitations, and possible applications of the paper. Although a conclusion may review the main points of the paper, do not replicate the abstract as the conclusion. A conclusion might elaborate on the importance of the work or suggest applications and extensions.

H2 is accepted: The influence of Complaints Handling on Customer Loyalty

The results of the mean complaint handling (X2) as a whole identify that complaint handling gets good grades. From the biggest mean, the third question is 4.49, namely Fave Hotel Kembangan handling complaints fairly without differentiating customers.

According to Mudie and Cottam in Tjiptono (2007), effective handling of complaints provides an opportunity to turn a dissatisfied customer into a satisfied company product / service customer (or even a lasting customer). If the handling of complaints given by the company is good, the customer will be loyal to the company.

This is supported by the results of previous studies by Supit (2015) which states that complaint handling has a positive effect on customer loyalty.

H3 is accepted: The influence of Customer Trust on Customer Loyalty

The results of the mean customer trust (X3) as a whole identify that customer trust gets good value. From the biggest mean, the second and fourth questions obtained by 4.46, namely Fave Hotel Kembangan has the responsibility of every problem that the customer faces and overall Fave Hotel Kembangan has the ability to meet the needs and desires of customers when staying.

According to Peelen and Beltman (2013) trust is a willingness to depend on partners who can be trusted. If the customer already believes in a company or product, the customer becomes loyal to the company.

This is supported by the results of previous studies by Supit (2015) that customer trust has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion of service quality, complaint handling, and customer trust in Fave Hotel Kembangan customer loyalty, the following conclusions can be drawn: 1) Service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty, which means that if the quality of service is improved, then Fave customers Hotel Kembangan will be more loyal. 2) Complaints handling has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty, which means that if good complaint handling is improved and maintained, customer loyalty to the Fave Hotel Kembangan will increase. 3) Customer trust has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty, which means that if the company maintains and increases customer trust, customer loyalty to Fave Hotel Kembangan will increase.

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